

GENETIC DIVERGENCE STUDIES IN PIGEONPEA [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millip]s]

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Abstract

The experiment was conducted during Kharif 2023 for study of genetic diversity of 42 genotypes of pigeonpea using D^2 statistics method of Mahalanobis. Genetic diversity of forty two genotypes of pigeonpea was accessed for nine characters in a randomized block design with two replications at Agriculture Research Station, Badnapur. Forty two genotypes of pigeonpea were grouped into nine clusters which indicated diversity. Cluster I had the 25 maximum number of genotypes, Cluster II had 10, while, Cluster III, IV, V, VI, VII, VIII, IX had 01 genotype each respectively. The greatest distance between two clusters was existed between cluster VIII and VII (37.77) indicating greatest divergence. The maximum intra-cluster distance of 14.49 was noticed in cluster II followed by 12.65 in cluster I. On the basis of genetic diversity analysis, high yielding diverse genotypes viz., PT-12-8-2, BDN-716, ICP-6992 of cluster I, ICP-4476, ICP-2641 of cluster II, ICP-1369 of VIII and BDN-2019-8 of cluster III.

Keywords: Pigeonpea, Genetic diversity, Clusters and D^2 Analysis.

Introduction

Pigeonpea [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp.] is grown as an annual crop despite being a short-lived perennial member of the fabaceae family. The cross pollination in pigeonpea found in the range of 20–70% . In India, 90% of the world's pigeonpea is produced, it is widely farmed. Methionine and cysteine are two amino acids that contain sulphur which is present in higher concentrations (about 25%) in the high protein genotypes (Singh et al. 1990). Seeds contain about 0.6 to 3.8 % lipids, 1.2 to 8.1 % crude fibre and 57.3 to 58.7 % carbohydrates (Sinha, 1977).

In a hybridization programme, genetic diversity is a prerequisite and a significant element. High yield improvement programs' success is mostly influenced by the kind and level of genetic variety and variability found in germplasm.

Materials and Methods

The research experiment was conducted at College of Agriculture, Badnapur during *kharif* 2023 in Randomized Block Design with two replications for nine quantitative characters viz, days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches per plant, number of pods per plant, number seeds per pod, 100 seed weight and seed yield per plant. Total forty two germplasm material constituted for research received from Agricultural Research Station, Badnapur including two checks. Each genotype sown in single row of 4 m length with row to row distance 90 cm and plant to plant distance 20 cm. Data were recorded for five selective plants from each genotype. The genetic diversity analysis will be carried out by D^2 statistical method as per by Mahalanobis (1936).

Result and Discussion

All the forty two genotypes of pigeonpea were grouped into nine clusters using the Toucher's method (Singh and Chaudhary, 1977). The result indicated that Cluster I had the maximum number of 25 germplasms, Cluster II had 10, Cluster III, IV, V, VI, VII, VIII and XI had 01 germplasm each respectively showed in Table 1. Result showed that genetic divergence in pigeonpea 42 genotypes were divided into 9 cluster, similarly result were was founded by Sreelakshmi *et al.* (2011), Kumara *et al.* (2013), Patel *et al.* (2018).

The least distance was recorded between cluster VII and IV (11.22) increases with cluster V and I (15.53), cluster VII and V (15.88) cluster V and VI (16.51) and indicating least genetic divergence among genotypes. Whereas The greatest distance between two clusters was existed between cluster VIII and VII (37.77) indicating greatest divergence, followed by cluster VIII and IV (35.70), cluster IX and VI (32.35), cluster VII and III (32.16) and cluster IV and III (31.67).

Intra and inter cluster distance showed in Table 2 and Fig 1. The intra cluster values varied from 0.00 to 14.49. The maximum intra-cluster distance of 14.49 was noticed in cluster II followed by 12.65 in cluster I. The genotypes belonging to these clusters can be considered as

parents for hybridization programme since genotypes within these clusters with a high degree of divergence would produce more desirable breeding material for achieving maximum genetic advance.

Cluster mean showed in Table 3. Highest cluster mean for plant height was found in cluster VIII (221.80) followed by cluster IV (216.40) while, lowest mean for plant height recorded in cluster IX (111.10). The least no. of primary branches mean was reported in cluster VIII (3.80). However cluster mean for primary branches was highest in cluster VII (11.55) followed by cluster IV (11.20). The maximum cluster mean for secondary branches was reported in cluster VII (27.75) followed by cluster VI (26.95) while minimum cluster mean for secondary branches was recorded in cluster VIII (7.30). The minimum mean recorded in cluster VII (3.50) while maximum mean for no. of seed per pod was reported in cluster VIII (5.45) followed by cluster IX (4.55). The least mean was recorded in cluster IV (7.15). While cluster mean for 100 seed weight was highest in cluster III (13.20) followed by cluster VIII (11.80). The maximum cluster mean for seed yield was recorded in cluster III (110.60) followed by cluster II (92.65) while minimum mean was recorded in cluster IX (15.61). Similar result were was found by Sreelakshmi *et al.* (2011), Kumara *et al.* (2013), Patel *et al.* (2018).

The utility of D^2 analysis is enhanced by its application to estimates the relative contribution of various characters to genetic diversity. The relative contribution of nine characters towards diversity was presented in Table 4. Number of pods per plant (36.47%) has the major contribution to total genetic diversity, seed index (26.25%), number of primary branches per plant (16.03%), number of secondary branches per. plant (8.83%), seed yield per plant (7.67%), number of seeds per pod (2.56%), plant height (1.97%), Days to maturity (0.23%), days to 50 % flowering (00.00%), negligible contribution towards the total genetic divergence.

Future scope of the study-

High yielding diverse genotypes viz., PT-12-8-2, BDN-716, ICP-6992 of cluster I, ICP-4476, ICP-2641 of cluster II, ICP-7057 of VIII and BDN-2019-8 of cluster III may be used for future hybridization program for further yield improvement in pigeonpea.

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Table 1. Composition of forty two pigeonpea genotypes into different clusters by Toucher’s Method.

Cluster number	No. of strains	Genotype included in the cluster
I	25	ICP-13564, ICP-14113, ICP-2630, ICP-12816, ICP-10331, ICP-13258, ICP-13732, BDN-2019-5, ICP-13579, ICP-12796, BDN-2018-37, Godavari , ICP-13270, PT-12-8-2, PT-2017-2, ICP-6519, ICP-6666, ICP-6427, PT-12-19, BDN-2019-34, PT-12-5-5, BDN-716, BDN-2013-45, ICP-6992, PT-2017-1.
II	10	ICP-2223, ICP-2641, ICP-4476, ICP-6536, ICP-6906, ICP-1355, ICP-1083, ICP-19720, ICP-6681, ICP-13082.
III	1	BDN-2019-8
IV	1	ICP-13011
V	1	ICP-14337
VI	1	ICP-6924
VII	1	ICP-3945
VIII	1	ICP-7057
IX	1	ICP-13191

Fig.1 Diagram Showing the Cluster Distance

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Table 2. Average cluster D² values of pigeonpea.

Cluster number	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
I	12.65	20.21	18.26	23.63	15.53	19.45	24.20	18.64	21.95
II		14.49	25.58	18.86	22.14	27.22	23.36	29.03	20.55
III			0	31.67	23.15	29.32	32.16	20.71	19.19
IV				0	16.63	24.21	11.22	35.70	27.68
V					0	16.51	15.88	25.26	27.50
VI						0	17.65	29.33	32.35
VII							0	37.77	31.37
VIII								0	24.83
IX									0

Table 3. Cluster means for Seed yield and its components in Pigeonpea.

Cluster	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant Height	Number of primary branches /plant	Number of secondary branches /plant	Number of pods /plant	Number of seeds /pod	100 seed weight	Seed Yield /plant
I	118.40	168.54	198.90	7.80	19.59	198.94	4.25	10.75	78.37
II	119.80	169.95	211.39	9.71	22.44	359.44	3.90	7.92	92.65
III	113.00	170.50	165.10	8.80	16.10	219.30	4.45	13.20	110.60
IV	113.00	166.50	216.40	11.20	23.05	188.70	3.75	7.15	49.61
V	131.00	177.00	206.50	9.20	18.80	81.40	3.70	11.05	32.60
VI	117.00	171.50	143.50	7.70	26.95	118.50	4.10	10.70	36.75
VII	124.00	170.50	158.15	11.55	27.75	167.60	3.50	8.50	47.00
VIII	123.00	171.50	221.80	3.80	7.30	52.40	5.45	11.80	31.85
IX	90.00	139.50	111.10	5.70	7.70	70.60	4.55	7.75	15.61

Table 4. Per cent contribution of different characters to genetic diversity.

Sr. no	Characters	No. of times appearing I in ranking	Contribution%
1	Days to 50% flowering	0	0.00%
2	Days to maturity	2	0.23%
3	Plant height (cm)	17	1.97%
4	Number of primary branches per plant	138	16.03%
5	Number of secondary branches per plant	76	8.83%
6	Number of pods per plant	314	36.47%
7	Number of seeds per pod	22	2.56%
8	100 seed weight (g)	226	26.25%
9	Seed yield per plant (g)	66	7.67%
10.	Total	861	100%